

A STUDY OF TEST ANXIETY AMONG HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

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Abstract:

Anxiety is a common phenomenon that constitutes a universal cause of poor academic performance among students worldwide. It is a kind of self preoccupation which is manifested as self- minimization and results in negative cognitive evaluation, lack of concentration, unfavorable physiological reactions and academic failure. Test anxiety and its dimensions became one of the broadest research areas in recent years. Compared to other students, most of the higher secondary students experience high levels of test anxiety during final exam even though their marks are good throughout the examinations. The study investigated differences in higher secondary students' overall test anxiety before, during, or after test taking among gender. Differences among test anxiety components were also examined. Participants were 300 higher secondary students (162 females, 138 males) school students from a Vellore city in Tamilnadu. The coded data were entered in to Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) version 20 for analysis. Mean and standard deviation were used to describe the data. In addition, t-test was used to see if there is statistically significant difference between higher secondary students. Results of this study concluded that a significant difference between of higher secondary students towards location of school in test anxiety and further it reveals there is no significant difference between higher secondary students towards gender and type of school in test anxiety.

Introduction:

Test anxiety has become a serious problem in contemporary society (Peleg, 2002) because of the ongoing importance of tests as part of assessments in education (Peleg, Deutch, & Dan 2016). In relation to the fact that potential advancement in modern society frequently depends on test performance (Peleg, 2004), test anxiety is a negative emotional response to current or prospective situation involving an evaluation. The effects of test anxiety are therefore educationally debilitating; students who suffer from test anxiety perform low, endorse poor competence beliefs, have strong failure appraisals and may even drop out of school altogether (Hembree, 1990). Yet, researchers have acknowledged that test anxiety mediated the influence of student emotions (e.g., negative affect, positive affect) on test performance. Nevertheless, the majority of studies have investigated test anxiety in terms of differences associated with gender (e.g., Everson, Millsap, & Rodriguez, 1991; Wigfield & Eccles, 1989); test anxiety research employing age and/or grade level differences that in a sense mirror the differences associated with school -level remains surprisingly sparse (Hembree, 1988).

Test anxiety is the other factor has been adduced for poor academic performance. It is generally accepted that it has a detrimental effect on test performance. Test anxiety individually varies in duration and also in intensity (Speilberger, 1979) and is comprised of at least two main components; worry and emotionality (Liebert & Morris, 1967).

Test anxiety is an undesirable reaction toward evaluation. It's the most important problem that is faced by the students in their education worldwide (Khosravi & Bigdeli, 2008). Test anxiety is a psychological condition in which students experience extreme distress and anxiety in test situations. A little anxiety during exams is required that will help students to get motivated and learn. Mounting up so much of anxiety will not help the student to perform rather it will influence the academic performance negatively (Coon & Mitterer, 2009). The psychological symptoms that build up in students before a test includes restlessness, unusual body movements, difficulty in concentrating, insomnia, fatigue, muscle contraction, abdominal pain, and tremors (Porto, 2013). These symptoms have negative consequences on student lives and professional growth.

Methodology: Normative survey method was followed.

Sample: The sample consists of 300 higher secondary students selected from the schools of Vellore district. Out of which 138 were boys and 162 were girls. The sample was collected by using multistage random sampling technique

Statement of the Problem: The problem chosen for the study may be stated as "A Study of Test Anxiety among Higher Secondary Students".

Statistical Techniques Used: The investigator used the statistical techniques, Mean, Standard Deviation 't' test and 'F' test to accept or reject hypotheses.

Data Analysis:

The data collected from the sample population were systematically coded, tabulated and organized for analysis. The coded data were entered in to Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) version 20 for analysis. Mean and standard deviation were used to describe the data. In addition, t-test was used to see if there is statistically significant difference between students actual and desired level of participation in test anxiety.

Description of Tool:

In the present study a tool on the test anxiety has been adopted which is in the form of questionnaire developed by (Nist and Diehl (1990) to collect the data. The tool is liket type which as five point rating scale such as never, rarely, sometimes, often, always.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To find out significant means score difference in test anxiety between boys and girls higher secondary students.
- ✓ To find out significant mean score difference in test anxiety between the rural and urban higher secondary students.
- ✓ To find out significant mean score difference in test anxiety between the government and private higher secondary students.

Hypotheses of the Study:

- ✓ There will be no significant means score difference in test anxiety between boys and girls higher secondary students.
- ✓ There will be no significant mean score difference in test anxiety between the rural and urban higher secondary students.
- ✓ There will be no significant mean score difference in test anxiety between the government and private higher secondary students.

Analysis of Data:

Table 1: “t” Test Between Male and Female Higher Secondary Students in their Test Anxiety

Gender	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated ‘t’- value	Remarks
Boys	138	29.32	3.633	1.041	NS
Girls	162	29.78	4.04		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of ‘t’ is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between boys and girls higher secondary students in their test anxiety.

Table 2: “t” Test between Rural and Urban Higher Secondary Students in their Test Anxiety

Location of School	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated ‘t’- value	Remarks
Rural	136	29.07	3.967	2.071	S
Urban	164	29.99	3.727		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of ‘t’ is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that there is significant difference between rural and urban location of school of higher secondary students in their test anxiety.

Table 3: “t” Test between Government and Private Higher Secondary Students in their Test Anxiety

Type of school	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated ‘t’- value	Remarks
Government	128	30.02	3.744	1.731	NS
Private	172	29.24	3.920		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of ‘t’ is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between government and private type of school of higher secondary students in their test anxiety.

Findings of the Study:

- ✓ It is found that there is no significant difference between boys and girls higher secondary students in their test anxiety.
- ✓ It is found that there is significant difference between rural and urban location of school of higher secondary students in their test anxiety.
- ✓ It is found that there is no significant difference between government and private type of school of higher secondary students in their test anxiety.

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